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Agriculture Growth and Rural Development in India

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Abstract

India is an agricultural country, in which agriculture plays an important role. About 16.8 percent of the world's population resides in our country India. About 69 percent of the country's population lives in rural areas and their main source of livelihood is agriculture and allied activities. The crop pattern includes Rabi, Kharif and Zaid crops, but there are many problems related to production in agriculture and agricultural economists have also accepted that high value of agricultural production, agricultural diversification will strengthen agricultural development in future and give high profits to farmers. Which will result in extensive employment opportunities and income flow, which will accelerate the pace of development in rural areas of India. The subject of my research paper is Agricultural Growth and Rural Development in India. This research paper shows the role of agriculture in agricultural growth and rural development in India and the role of diversification to develop the agricultural sector.

Keywords Agriculture, Rural Development, High Value Commodities.

Introduction

Agriculture is the major source of livelihood in the rural sector. Mahatma Gandhi once said that the real progress of India did not mean simply the growth and expansion of industrial urban centers but mainly the development of the villages. This idea of village development being at the centre of the overall development of the nation is relevant even today. Why is this so? Why should we attach such significance to rural development when we see around us fast growing cities with large industries and modern information technology hubs? It is because more than two-third of India's population depends on agriculture that is yet to become productive enough to provide for them; one-fourth of rural India still lives in abject poverty. That is the reason why we have to see a developed rural India if our nation has to realize real progress. What, then, does rural development imply?

Objective of study

The paper will enshrine role of agriculture in rural development and role of diversification to develop agriculture sector itself and is based on secondary data sources, NSSO, Census data is being used in the paper.

Review of Literature

Rural development is a comprehensive term. It essentially focuses on action for the development of areas that are lagging behind in the overall development of the village economy. Some of the areas which are challenging and need fresh initiatives for development in rural India include

1. Development of human resources including
2. Literacy, more specifically, female literacy, education and skill development.
3. Health, addressing both sanitation and public health
4. Land reforms
5. Development of the productive resources of each locality

6. Infrastructure development like electricity, irrigation, credit, marketing, transport facilities including construction of village roads and feeder roads to nearby highways, facilities for agriculture research and extension, and information dissemination

Rural development is quite a comprehensive term but it essentially means a plan of action for the development of rural areas which are lagging behind in socio-economic development.

Main Text

Solutions and Recommended Actions

There is a need for improving the quantity and quality of infrastructure in rural areas such as banking, marketing, storage, transport and communications etc. to realise its true potential.

Credit and Marketing In Rural Areas

Credit: Growth of rural economy depends primarily on infusion of capital, from time to time, to realize higher productivity in agriculture and non-agriculture sectors. As the time gestation between crop sowing and realisation of income after production is quite long, farmers borrow from various sources to meet their initial investment on seeds, fertilisers, implements and other family expenses of marriage, death, religious ceremonies etc.

Rural Banking -ba Critical Appraisal

Rapid expansion of the banking system had a positive effect on rural farm and non-farm output, income and employment, especially after the green revolution — it helped farmers to avail services and credit facilities and a variety of loans for meeting their production needs. Famines became events of the past; we have now achieved food security which is reflected in the abundant buffer stocks of grains.

Agricultural Market System

Agricultural marketing is a process that involves the assembling, storage, processing, transportation, packaging, grading and distribution of different agricultural commodities across the country.

Emerging Alternate Marketing

Channels: It has been realized that if farmers directly sell their produce to consumers, it increases their incomes.

Further, several national and multinational fast food chains are increasingly entering into contracts/ alliances with farmers to encourage them to cultivate farm products (vegetables, fruits, etc.) of the desired quality by providing them with not only seeds and other inputs but also assured procurement of the produce at predecided prices.

Diversification Into Productive Activities

Diversification includes two aspects - one relates to change in cropping pattern and the other relates to a shift of workforce from agriculture to other allied activities (livestock, poultry, fisheries etc.) and non-agriculture sector. The need for diversification arises from the fact that there is greater risk in depending exclusively on farming for livelihood. Diversification towards new areas is necessary not only to reduce the risk from agriculture sector but also to provide productive sustainable livelihood options to rural people. Much of the agricultural employment activities are concentrated in the Kharif season. But during the Rabi season, in areas where there are inadequate irrigation facilities, it becomes difficult to find gainful employment. Therefore expansion into other sectors is essential to provide supplementary gainful employment and in realising higher levels of income for rural people to overcome poverty and other tribulations. Hence, there is a need to focus on allied activities, non-farm employment and other emerging alternatives of livelihood, though there are many other options available for providing sustainable livelihoods in rural areas.

Diversification towards new areas such as livestock, fisheries and other non-agricultural activities is necessary not only to reduce the risk from agriculture sector but also to provide productive sustainable livelihood options to our rural people.

The importance of organic farming as an environmentally sustainable production process is on a rise and needs to be promoted.

Miscellaneous Recommended Actions

1. Reorient social safety nets to create more employment in rural areas; help strengthen the human resource base through education, nutrition, and empowerment of women; and build physical infrastructure.
2. Reform water management and institutions and design water pricing systems on the basis of water rights to cope with increasingly scarce water supplies for agriculture.
3. Exploit new opportunities to participate in the production and marketing of high-value livestock products, fruits and vegetables, and fishery.

Conclusion

In an agricultural country like India, agricultural development and rural development are interlinked. The agricultural sector not only ensures food security of the country, but also provides employment to the rural population. Agricultural production has increased significantly through the Green Revolution, technological innovations, improvements in irrigation systems, and government schemes. At the same time, significant progress has also been made in areas such as roads, health, education, electricity, and digital connectivity towards rural development.

However, problems still persist — such as climate change, deterioration in land quality, problems of small and marginal farmers, and unemployment among rural youth. To address these, a holistic and sustainable development is needed, which includes empowering farmers economically and making development plans at the local level.

Thus, it can be said that the holistic and balanced development of India is possible only when the agricultural sector is modernized and the social and economic infrastructure in rural areas is strengthened. The goal of self-reliant India and sustainable development can be achieved only by advancing agriculture and rural development simultaneously.

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